

Examining emotional intelligence evolution with age: insights from Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs of different generations

IIMT Journal of
Management

5

Ana Todorova
University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", Ruse, Bulgaria

Received 25 December 2023

Revised 1 March 2024

20 April 2024

Accepted 16 May 2024

Abstract

Purpose – This article aims to explore the relationship between age and emotional intelligence, as the latter emerges as essential to professional performance and an individual's ability to adapt to an ever-changing world. The study examines the emotional intelligence of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs from different generations.

Design/methodology/approach – The developed methodology for studying the emotional intelligence of digital business owners is based on Daniel Goleman's model of emotional intelligence. The sample consists of 1,175 participants; the statistical error for the studied population is 2.8%. The demographic groups covered by the study are as follows: 1965 (Baby Boomers); 1965–1979 (Generation X); 1980–1995 (Generation Y); and 1995 (Generation Z). Data were collected using an anonymous form and subsequently analysed.

Findings – The comparison between the different generations of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs reflects an increasing trend with age in the ability to exercise and apply emotional intelligence. The findings also show that although emotional intelligence is seen as the result of five components – self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills, the predominance of only one of these competencies does not guarantee high emotional intelligence. At the same time, self-awareness stands out as an ever-evolving component of emotional intelligence.

Originality/value – This paper integrates the concept of the development of emotional intelligence with age and confirms that general emotional intelligence may increase with age. Therefore, the study adds value to the literature on entrepreneurship, organisational behaviour and human resource management.

Keywords Emotional intelligence, Digital entrepreneurs, Generation

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) has been identified as vital to human interactions, so its role *in and for* the work environment has received significantly more attention in recent years. Individuals with higher EI scores are believed to suffer from less stress and show better professional performance, including in managerial roles (Xue *et al.*, 2023). Increased EI is also directly related to improved health and subjective well-being (Fernández-Martínez *et al.*, 2019). A significant number of studies derive as a main conclusion the statement that a high ability of emotional perception is related to improving managers' performance (Wezowski and Penton-Voak, 2023; Gottfredson and Becker, 2023; Xue *et al.*, 2023).

Borrajó *et al.* (2023) point to the appropriate cognition, identification, and regulation of emotions as effective mechanisms not only in occupational fulfilment but also in various other contexts: problematic Internet use, cyberbullying, or burnout, as well as in various

© Ana Todorova. Published in *IIMT Journal of Management*. Published by Emerald Publishing Limited. This article is published under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) licence. Anyone may reproduce, distribute, translate and create derivative works of this article (for both commercial and non-commercial purposes), subject to full attribution to the original publication and authors. The full terms of this licence may be seen at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

IIMT Journal of Management

Vol. 1 No. 1, 2024

pp. 5-23

Emerald Publishing Limited

e-ISSN: 2976-727X

p-ISSN: 2976-7261

DOI 10.1108/IIMTJM-12-2023-0075

mental disorders such as eating disorders, anxiety, depression and suicidal behaviour. Thus, EI can be presented as an important factor that allows the individual to adapt to a stressful environment and acts as a protective element against it. In addition to helping to improve emotional skills and increase social skills, [Fernández-Martínez et al. \(2023\)](#) present significant evidence that EI is a protective factor against technological addictions.

All this highlights the need to know the specifics of EI, including the study of emotion management in the context of different demographic groups, in order to understand human developmental trajectories across the lifespan. [Galdona et al. \(2018\)](#) are of the opinion that the study of the development of EI with age is necessary because age has been shown to be a modulating variable, which means that strategies must be developed to adapt the individual during each stage of life. Specific skills such as EI and the competencies that build it are fundamental to a healthier psychological, social and physical life. The emphasis is on older generations who have to cope with various physical, social, and personal challenges in an atypical for them digital age. The latter often leads to social exclusion or imputation of a sense of unworthiness in older generations, which could be reduced with the development of a more emotionally intelligent society. Therefore, psychological intervention and skill-building programs must focus on teaching EI competence with a lifelong perspective because when EI is improved through training, psychological, physical, and social adaptation is also enhanced.

That demonstrates, on the one hand, the importance of EI for the development of more prosperous and healthy societies and, on the other hand, the need for a deeper study of the concept of EI in order to better understand and implement it in the individual's life ([Di Fabio and Kenny, 2016](#)). Part of this understanding includes the topic of the evolution of EI with age. Such knowledge would confirm that EI possesses the ability to change; therefore, it would further improve programs and models for recognising and managing emotions. The question is whether age is a significant influencing factor for change or time as a continuum.

The inquiry into the relationship between emotional intelligence and age is also becoming increasingly relevant in the face of an ageing population. It has profound implications for organisations as the workforce is also ageing, coupled with ever-increasing emotional demands on employees ([Atkins and Con, 2005](#)). At the same time, the digital economy has steadily become vital for growth and jobs. Undoubtedly, the invasion of digital technologies is having a significant impact on the labour market, the forms of entrepreneurship and business start-ups, and the type of skills needed in the economy and society ([Move, 2017](#)). Every technological innovation leaves a dramatic imprint on an individual's thinking and lifestyle and affects his social relationships, self-esteem and development as a person.

Today, life without digitisation is unthinkable. That gave impetus to a new type of entrepreneurial initiative, implemented entirely or partially in a digital environment, forming the so-called digital entrepreneurship. It is much more than just creating one's own business in a digital environment – it is a way of thinking, a culture of behaviour, an attitude, and a flexible approach to various issues by adapting to a constantly changing environment. Digital entrepreneurship is becoming a norm and an economic factor no less than traditional entrepreneurship ([Move, 2017](#)).

Considering that emotional intelligence is among the most necessary skills of the future, and digital entrepreneurship is the new business reality, the author chooses to investigate this particular entrepreneurial group and to what extent the age of the individual entrepreneur influences the specific dimensions and competencies of emotional intelligence. Confirmation that EI has the potential to increase or change over time is a valuable contribution to the literature on organisational behaviour, entrepreneurship, and human resource management.

The manuscript's structure adheres to the following logic: first, a literature review of the conceptualisation of emotional intelligence and existing research related to the research object – increasing EI with age – is presented. The research methodology is then described,

and the results are analysed and discussed. Finally, the study's main conclusions are described, highlighting the importance of knowing the evolution of EI, the study's main limitations and possible future lines of research.

2. Literature review

According to Mayer and Salovey's definition, EI is an individual's ability to recognise and monitor one's own and others' emotions and to use this information to influence one's own and others' thoughts and actions (Gottfredson and Becker, 2023). The concept of EI gained widespread attention and spread in many fields after the publication in 1995 of the book *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ?* Its author, Daniel Goleman, an American psychologist, claims that in addition to being rational, a person also has a *mental* mind, and both of them store memories that influence human behaviour (Kuday and Erdoğan, 2023).

EI is a popular topic among both the general public and academics. Atkins and Con (2005) consider that this is probably due to the intuitive idea that emotions play an essential role in success in various aspects of life, such as:

- (1) *Leadership* – effective leaders are able to motivate and inspire others as well as manage conflict;
- (2) *Workplace performance* – people with high EI tend to be more productive, creative and adaptable;
- (3) *Life satisfaction* – EI can help people build healthier and more satisfying relationships.

In addition, previous studies have found that higher EI is associated with building and forming positive relationships with others and the size of the social network of contacts (Goleman, 2011; Barr, 2023). In comparison, lower EI leads to interpersonal conflicts and communication problems (Xue *et al.*, 2023). The question arises: is it possible to move emotional intelligence from low to high values, and does the age of the individual determine this process?

Regardless of the composition of EI, most authors and concepts are united around the statement that there is a positive relationship between EI and age (Phillips *et al.*, 2002; Anwar, 2010; Goleman, 2011; Galdona *et al.*, 2018). During different periods, measures of emotional intelligence have reported that older adults score significantly higher than younger adults on EI and emotional understanding (Phillips *et al.*, 2002; Anwar, 2010; Galdona *et al.*, 2018). At the same time, there is another point of view, although less prevalent. According to her, an individual's emotional quotient – an analogue of EI (Cherry, 2024) and an example of EI in action (Bariso, 2020) – is a fairly stable indicator and difficult to change (Kennedy, n.d; Chamorro-Premuzic, 2013; Kennedy, 2020).

According to Sharma (2017) and Gottfredson and Becker (2023) argue that not only does EI develop or increase with age and experience, but certain aspects of EI can only be developed with training. Although there is a paucity of studies on the issue, research on EI gradually expands the age range to include older (over 50 years) people (Anwar, 2010; Humintell, 2011; Galdona *et al.*, 2018). These studies found that older adults scored significantly higher EI than young adults. EI was configured similarly in middle-aged adults (50–65) and older adults (66–90). A 2009 study from the University of California, Berkeley, also confirmed that emotional intelligence peaks when people enter their 60s (Humintell, 2011). Galdona *et al.* (2018) explain this positive relationship between age and EI through lifelong learning and accumulated knowledge and experience.

Di Fabio and Kenny (2016) cite research with young adults in Belgium, showing that EI can be improved with targeted training. Subsequent research applying the same EI intervention with Belgian students revealed that the benefits of developing EI led to positive changes in personality characteristics. EI promotes students' psychological well-being and enables them to understand the environment around them better, providing them with the skills they need to cope with everyday situations. It is crucial to develop these emotional skills during the university stage, as they would enable students to achieve better academic results and adapt to the different contexts they will later encounter in the world of work. Therefore, they will be better prepared for the future society (Fernández-Martínez *et al.*, 2023) thanks to their emotional intelligence as adults.

Chen *et al.* (2016) also claim that lifelong learning and accumulated knowledge can explain the positive relationship between age and EI. Most types of intelligence, including EI, can be improved through practice, meaning that older adults have more opportunities than young adults to practice emotional intelligence throughout their lives. Therefore, older adults better understand emotions and use better emotion regulation strategies than younger adults. Perhaps this explains why younger generations are more expressive in their behaviour, while over the years, expressiveness gradually turns into restraint (Freedman, 2021).

A similar opinion is shared by Smith (2018), according to whom EI must be perceived as a skill that, like wisdom, can be developed throughout life. While some people can fully grasp a skill easily, others need training, practice and experience to grasp the concept. Therefore, EI must be taught and modelled throughout childhood, from kindergarten through high school. Studies show that emotionally intelligent children grow up to be emotionally intelligent adults. Such children have the opportunity to improve this critical skill set over time and, as a result, develop emotional wisdom for a lifetime.

The claim makes it possible to correlate between two seemingly independent paradigms – *emotional intelligence* and *wisdom* (Smith, 2018). Wisdom is defined as the ability to act critically or practically in a given situation and is based on ethical judgement related to an individual's belief system (Jakubik and Müürsepp, 2022). Emotional intelligence is associated with recognising, interpreting and managing emotions, as these skills improve decision-making, active listening, critical thinking and empathic behaviour, which *may* or *may not* support ethical judgements and decisions (Cherry, 2023).

Chamorro-Premuzic (2013) argues that one's ability to identify and manage one's own and other's emotions is relatively stable over time, influenced by our early childhood experiences and even genetics. That does not mean it cannot change, but realistically, long-term improvements will require a lot of dedication and guidance. For him, *time*, not *age*, is the significant factor. The author nevertheless shares the widely held view that the emotional quotient tends to increase with age, even without intentional interventions. That, he argues, is the technical way of saying that people *mature* with age.

Kennedy (2020) takes the firm position that EI cannot be improved – with age or through training. According to the scientist, the reason lies in the difference between psychology and neurology. Emotion is a neurological response to an environmental trigger before the brain is even conscious. It is only after a neurophysiological change is realised in the person – an increase in heart rate, sweating, or an increased rate of breathing – that a feeling occurs that follows this initial emotional trigger in the brain. However, the inability to control the emotional trigger in the brain remains. Instead, the individual can become aware of and change the way they *feel*. In fact, Kennedy does not dispute whether or not EI can change. According to him, it is correct to talk about *feeling intelligence* and not emotional, as *feeling intelligence*, the author claims, is subject to modification through various practices.

Taking into account the different perspectives and focusing on specific generational groups engaged in digital entrepreneurship in Bulgaria, the study seeks answers to the following research questions (RQ):

- RQ1. Does the EI of Bulgarian digital entrepreneur evolve with age and the change of generations?
- RQ2. Do one or more of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs' EI competencies stand out as sustainable and upwardly changing over time?

3. Research methodology

The study adheres to [Goleman's, 2011](#) model of EI, which consists of five domains:

- (1) *Self-awareness* – understanding one's own emotions;
- (2) *Self-regulation* – controlling one's own emotions;
- (3) *Motivation* – channelling emotions to achieve goals;
- (4) *Empathy* – understanding the emotions of others;
- (5) *Social skills* – using emotions to build relationships.

The choice of Goleman's model for the current study is due to its mixed nature. According to Goleman, EI is, on the one hand, an ability that can be acquired and, on the other, a personal characteristic that can develop over time ([Goleman, 2011](#)). Unlike the different models, according to which EI is either only a personal characteristic – Petrides and Furnham, or only a cognitive ability – Mayer and Salovey ([Kostadinova, 2019](#)). According to [Kostadinova \(2019\)](#), Goleman's model does not only focus on the theoretical definition of EI but also on the practical skills that are necessary for its successful application, which is why the measurement of EI is carried out through self-assessment or situational tests. The most significant advantage of the model is that the author of the concept does not oppose the cognitive and emotional aspects of intelligence but considers them as interconnected and complementary.

Essentially, in his model, Goleman mainly covers *self-motivation*. However, the author of the present study believes that from the point of view of entrepreneurship and leadership, the ability to motivate employees and teams successfully is no less essential. Thus, in the study, motivation is divided into *Self-motivation* – optimism or the ability to motivate oneself, and *Motivation* – the ability to encourage others.

Questions from *Professional emotional intelligence tests* by [Wood and Tolley \(2003\)](#) were used. The two experts do not claim accurate measurements given the nature of the research object but are confident that their tests can reasonably accurately estimate EI. After completing the questionnaire, each respondent's EI was calculated based on the degree of manifestation of each competency and classified as high, medium, or low on a predetermined scale by Wood and Tolley.

The study was conducted from *January 25th – March 25th, 2021*, and aimed at digital entrepreneurs operating from Bulgaria and developing in various directions. The research seeks to establish the level of emotional intelligence and the manifestation of its inherent competencies in digital entrepreneurship by showing whether there is a change. The selection of the group of respondents was made considering the growing importance of digital entrepreneurship in Bulgaria. Without a doubt, digital business models are having a significant impact on human resources and the type of skills needed by employees and entrepreneurs ([Move, 2017](#)). That suggests a greater interest in the emotional intelligence of those building the Bulgarian digital economy.

The general population is 42,238 enterprises. It was formed by 38,238 enterprises, representing 10.9%, offering goods and services online (NSI, 2021; NSI, 2022) – out of a total of 350,804 active enterprises in Bulgaria, according to NSI data and 4,000 freelance developers and engineers in Bulgaria (DEV, 2021). The minimum sample volume is 381 at a confidence level of 95%. The sample consists of 1,175 participants; the statistical error for the studied population is 2.8%.

The demographic groups covered by the study are in line with the most common generational division (in Bulgaria) of: < 1965 (Baby Boomers); 1965–1979 (Generation X); 1980–1995 (Generation Y); and 1995 > (Generation Z). According to a 2019 study by marketing agency Noema (Economy), 72% of Bulgaria’s population falls into these four “categories”, the distribution being respectively: Baby Boomers – 21% of Bulgarians, Generation X – 22%, Generation Y – 20%, and Generation Z – 9%.

The survey form was prepared with the toolkit of the Google Forms web application and contains 42 questions relevant to the purpose and tasks of the study, of which 39 are closed-ended. The questions are prepared in Bulgarian, the official language of the Republic of Bulgaria. The form has been tested by seven experts, five of whom are digital entrepreneurs and two university professors. After the testing, the number of questions was kept the same because the survey constructed in this way contains the minimum possible number of questions necessary for the objectivity of the research. Added: a) clarifying texts about the relevance and authors of the questions; b) a short explanatory PDF material regarding EI to make the research topic more accessible; c) at the end of the survey form, PDF materials and articles on the topic of marketing, blockchain and digital professions have been added to motivate respondents and thank them for their time.

In conducting research, the author invested personal time and no financial resources. The survey was carried out by distributing the link to the survey form among professional groups of digital entrepreneurs on social networks, personal contacts with entrepreneurs developing digital businesses, and professional connections with various associations, which include a link to the survey in their official newsletter, among them Bulgarian Chamber of Commerce and Industry and Bulgarian E-commerce Association; among opinion leaders (influencers and bloggers).

Taking into account the existing literature on the topic of EI, it can be assumed that the study will: (1) find a proportional correlation between the age of the respondents and their EI, (2) identify at least one of the components of EI as significant for the growth of EI.

The conceptual framework of the study is visually presented in Figure 1. Data processing was performed using Excel tools for mathematical and statistical functions. Analyses and summaries are presented in the Results and Discussion sections.

Source(s): The author

Figure 1.
The conceptual
framework of the study

4. Results

The survey covered 1,175 respondents, of whom 791 were women (67.3% of the respondents) and 384 were men, making up 32.7% of those who participated in the study (Figure 2). The number of people who marked the option *I do not want to answer* is 0.

On the question *You were born* (Figure 3):

- (1) the most respondents – 627 or 53.4% of those who participated, marked the option *between 1980 and 1995*;
- (2) 292 respondents, or 24.9%, indicated the demographic group *between 1965 and 1979*;
- (3) slightly less – 245 respondents, or 20.9%, indicated an answer *after 1995*,
- (4) and 11 people or 0.9% of the respondents were born *before 1965*.

According to the data presented by Noema (Economy, 2019), Bulgarians belonging to Generation X are twice as many as those belonging to Generation Z. Still, according to the present study, the digital entrepreneurs who took part in the research and belong to these two age groups are close in number. That shows a much greater interest in digital opportunities among Gen Z than in previous generations. That is an expected result since, according to the study cited above, Generation Z are *creative and entrepreneurial, seek satisfaction in their work and are addicted to the Internet and technology* – 99% of them surf the web daily.

Digital entrepreneurs from Generation Y have the largest share in the survey – just over half of the respondents. Dimock (2019) calls this generation *growing up in an “always on” technological environment*, which explains the high rate of digital (self) employment among those born between 1980 and 1995. Fuchs (2022) claims that Generation Y is characterised by a desire to acquire new knowledge and upgrade existing skills, predetermining their sustainable competitive advantage in the labour market and the search for new opportunities. The latter most likely applies in full to the options provided by developing digital and information technologies. Baby Boomers, on the other hand, had the lowest number of respondents, and this is probably related to the fact that they are defined as the digitally slowest generation, although they are no less educated and entrepreneurial than the rest of the demographic groups (Medium, 2018).

4.1 Self-awareness

An individual's clarity about his unconscious emotional states, conscious feelings, and the role of broader life circumstances is the first step toward channelling emotions constructively and in the right direction

Source(s): The author

Figure 2.
Distribution of survey
respondents by gender

Figure 3.
Distribution of survey respondents by age

■ Before 1965 - 11 people (0.9%)
 ■ Between 1965 and 1979 - 292 people (24.9%)
 ■ Between 1980 and 1995 - 627 people (53.4%)
 ■ After 1995 - 245 (20.9%)

Source(s): The author

Self-knowledge or *self-awareness* is about being open to different experiences and new ideas and learning from social contacts and influences (Craig, 2019). *Self-awareness* means a deep understanding of one's emotions, strengths and weaknesses, needs and aspirations, and their effect on others. Characteristics of a self-aware individual include self-confidence, realistic self-esteem, and a self-deprecating sense of humour (Reilly and Karounos, 2009).

Figure 4 graphically presents the distribution in percentages of the degree of self-awareness according to the respondents of a given age group. At first glance, it can be seen as a negative trend – self-awareness as competence decreases with each subsequent generation: from over 71% of highly self-aware entrepreneurs of the Baby Boomers generation to 50% of the Z generation.

From another point of view, the result can be taken as evidence for one of the main distinguishing conditions between rational and emotional intelligence, namely that EI can change and increase with age, as the trend of change (Figure 5) of competence Self-awareness shows it most definitely. It is possible to assume that the main reason for EI to change is because of the ability of self-consciousness to be upgraded. Years of experience transform the individual into an increasingly conscious, emotionally-intelligent state.

Figure 4.
Level of developed competence self-awareness – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

Source(s): The author

Source(s): The author

Figure 5. Change trend of highly self-aware digital entrepreneurs by age

4.2 Self-control

The ability to regulate emotions is a uniquely human trait. Most animals respond immediately and without disguising the emotion that arises in them and humans can moderate, intensify, simulate, or suppress the emotion

Self-regulation or self-control is the ability to manage or redirect destructive impulses and moods and the tendency to suspend judgement – to think before acting. Characteristics include reliability, integrity and comfort with ambiguity, and openness to change (Reilly and Karounos, 2009). In the comparative analysis of the data by Self-Control and Age Group indicators (Figure 6), representatives of the X Generation have an advantage – 69.75% of them have the ability to self-regulate their behaviour to a high degree. The results of Generation Y – 63.21%, and those born before 1965 – 66.67%, are close.

Generation Z has a lower score – 56.26%, and this difference can again be looked at from two sides: whether the potential dilution of values such as honesty and reliability in each subsequent generation does not also lead to a decrease in the ability to self-regulate, or,

Source(s): The author

Figure 6. Level of developed competence self-control – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

similarly of the self-knowledge indicator, again there is a tendency to improve this competence with age? Depending on the cultural and other differences between diverse countries and regions, it is possible to admit both points of view.

4.3 Optimism

The willingness to make efforts to achieve some goals. It is the driving force that initiates and directs human behaviour

Optimism, in this case, self-motivation, is defined as a passion to work for reasons beyond money or status, with a tendency to pursue goals with energy and persistence. Characteristics of a motivated, emotionally intelligent leader are a strong desire to achieve, optimism – even in the face of failure – and organisational commitment (Reilly and Karounos, 2009). Goleman (2011) defines optimism as an inexhaustible source of motivation. From the perspective of EI, it is a skill that saves people from apathy, hopelessness, or depression and is an essential tool for dealing with problems.

The *Optimism* indicator in the current study refers to the entrepreneur’s internal motivation – what drives him in his endeavours – money and material rewards, or passion for what he does. Again, according to Goleman (2011), passion underpins better EI and leads to sustained motivation, transparent decision-making, and a better understanding of the organisation’s goals.

In the analysis by age demographic (Figure 7), although representatives of Generation X are the most internally motivated – 71.91%, no specific leader can be identified, as the results are close – 69.7% among Baby Boomers, 66.21% among Generation Y and 64.08% among those born after 1995.

A possible explanation for such similarity is again given by Goleman (2011), according to whom the negative or positive attitude to life and circumstances can be due to innate temperament. He thinks that, to some extent, some people are naturally inclined to react one way or the other. Therefore, *optimism* may be an innate trait and is not that much affected by an individual’s age. At the same time, it is impressive that the Baby Boomer and X Generations, who went through the most challenging years of a totalitarian regime and the subsequent transition to democracy in Bulgaria, have preserved their optimism to the highest degree. This historical period is also a possible explanation for the outstanding self-control of the same two generations who grew up in times of deprivation and strict discipline. Part of

Figure 7.
Level of developed competence optimism – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

Source(s): The author

Generation Y is also affected by these political regimes, but the consequence is less pronounced in their lives and development.

4.4 Motivation

The ability to motivate others is not explicitly stated in Goleman’s model, as it is rather a cumulative result of the other competencies. The data analysis on the *Motivation* and *Age Group* indicators (Figure 8) shows that the ability to motivate others is least developed among digital entrepreneurs belonging to the Baby Boomer Generation – below 40%. This percentage is similar among Generations X and Y – over 67% for the former and 61% for the latter, and drops to below 54% for the youngest survey respondents. When compared with the data from Figure 6, it was observed that those born before 1965 were more *optimistic and self-motivated* (69.7%) compared to their ability to influence others positively (39.39%).

4.5 Empathy

Sensing the feelings of others and seeing things from their perspective. Contemporary concepts of leadership and business effectiveness invariably include empathy and empathic leadership

Empathy, the fourth component of Goleman’s model, is understanding other people’s emotions and relating to them according to their emotional responses. Applicability is noticed in communication and customer service, cross-cultural sensitivity, and experience building and retaining talent (Reilly and Karounos, 2009). *Empathy* is essential for entrepreneurs, and leaders with empathy can put themselves in someone else’s shoes and help develop the people on their team (MindTools, n.d.).

By generational groups, empathy is highly developed in Generations X – 68.89%, Y – 61.96% and Z – 61.5% in a relatively close range (Figure 9). The deviation, similar to the previous indicator, Motivation, is in the generation of Baby Boomers, where the share of entrepreneurs with middle-developed empathy (50%) is higher than that of respondents who can fully sense the feelings of others (42.42%).

4.6 Social skills

Relationship management to increase collaboration and resolve disputes

Social skills, or the final component of EI, are skills for managing relationships and building networks, with the ability to find common ground and build rapport. Characteristics

Source(s): The author

Figure 8. Level of developed competence motivation – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

Figure 9.
Level of developed competence empathy – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

Source(s): The author

include effectiveness in leading change, persuasiveness, and experience in building and leading teams (Reilly and Karounos, 2009). Leaders with excellent social skills are defined as effective communicators who are good at managing change and resolving conflict (MindTools, no date).

Social skills are developed in the highest percentage among the representatives of Generation X – 62.39% of respondents in this age group possess the skill of effective communication and good interaction with others (Figure 10). Among those born after 1980 (i.e. generations Y and Z), this competence is manifested to the highest degree by slightly more than half of the respondents – over 55%, and among those born before 1965 – the percentage is slightly below 44%.

4.7 Emotional intelligence

Based on the individual results for each personal competence, the relative share of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs possessing the highest degree of developed *Emotional intelligence* and its inherent competencies can be presented according to their age.

The data summarised in Table 1, shows that Generation X has the most highly developed EI – over 67% possess developed EI competencies. The Baby Boomer Generation is the only leader in the *Self-awareness* indicator, confirming that this competence can be developed

Figure 10.
Level of developed competence social skills – high, medium and low, summarized by demographic groups

Source(s): The author

throughout the individual's life cycle. By all other indicators, the preponderance is for Generation X.

The comparison between generations X, Y and Z reflects a growing trend in the ability to exercise and apply EI and its inherent competencies. It also positively answers the first research question (*Does the EI of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs evolve with age and generational change?*). Although, in a number of cases, the values are close, it is evident that EI competencies improve from youth (below 28 years) to maturity (in the range of 29 years to about 59 years). There is either a slight increase with age or relative stability in the competencies of the age group formed by generations X and Y.

The research shows that respondents belonging to the group of the oldest digital entrepreneurs – the Baby Boomers – have the lowest percentage of highly developed EI. In the meantime, the number of respondents from this generational group is insufficient to ensure representativeness and allow general conclusions. At the same time, the reasons for the variance in outcomes among Baby Boomers can be sought in many directions, including cultural differences, historical burden, family trauma and upbringing, political regime, and education system. Confirmation is found in recent research by [Gottfredson and Becker \(2023\)](#), according to which past psychological traumas cause neural adaptations that hinder individuals' EI abilities. The authors point out that over 70% of adults have experienced significant psychological trauma and provide evidence that EI has a strong neural component, calling into question general skill development efforts designed to improve EI.

In addition, is it correct to assume that if EI develops with age, then the oldest generation, the baby boomers, will have the highest EI compared to other generations? As [Johnson et al. \(2012\)](#) point out, contrary to popular belief, evolution is not necessarily progressive – “*evolution of life takes many directions, not all of which are toward more complexity or progress*”. Therefore, in a broader sense, evolution can also be perceived as a *process of change*. Change is not necessarily upward and does not always equate to *improvement*. How does the human body evolve with age? From growth to decline, no doubt. The reported decrease in EI levels in baby boomers may reflect a cognitive change similar to a physical one – perhaps there is a point in time when EI begins to decline, similar to the ageing human body. Based on the current sample of respondents from the Baby Boomer generation, the author does not allow such a conclusion but offers a different perspective.

Despite the limitations of the present study, a similar finding, called *concerning*, was also observed in the results of the most extensive EI study – *State of the Heart*, launched in 2011 and based on a random sample of 129 countries. [Freedman \(2021\)](#) points out that while society expects higher levels of compassion and concern in older generations and, therefore, higher levels of empathy, the *State of the Heart* study reveals that Baby Boomers are more oriented towards self-awareness rather than empathy. This combination can lead to self-centeredness and hinder this generation's ability to lead at a time when the world urgently needs empathetic leadership.

Indicators	<1965	1965–1979	1980–1995	1995 >
Self-awareness	71.21%	65.98%	57.60%	50.61%
Self-control	66.67%	69.75%	63.21%	56.26%
Optimism	69.70%	71.91%	66.21%	64.08%
Motivation	39.39%	67.52%	61.54%	53.88%
Empathy	42.42%	68.89%	61.96%	61.50%
Social skills	43.94%	62.39%	55.45%	55.65%
High EI	55.56%	67.74%	61.00%	57.00%

Source(s): The author

Table 1.
Summary data for the
emotional intelligence
of all study
participants, grouped
by age

The study provides a definitive answer to the second research question: *Do one or more of the EI competencies of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs stand out as sustainable and upwardly changing over time?* The self-awareness indicator shows the desired evolution over the years, and its development increases with age. This competence is associated with understanding both mood and thoughts about the self, and research data shows that this knowledge increases with age. That underlines the connection between EI and wisdom found in the literary background. In addition, from the point of view of self-observation, allowing impartial awareness of passions and anxieties (Goleman, 2011), EI could be defined as a necessary skill for individuals of different ages to deal with crises and conflicts, as well as for adaptation to a constantly changing environment.

5. Discussion

The study confirms the significant stability of EI scores as a trait over different periods, including long-term and different intervals, achieved in analogous studies. That is consistent with results that define emotional aspects of personality and consistently find high levels of trait stability across adulthood (Zadorozhny *et al.*, 2024). Similar is the observation regarding the respondents of Generation X, who demonstrate stability in all the studied indicators.

The self-control of Baby Boomers can also be cited as a relatively well-developed skill and allows them to take second place in this indicator. A possible explanation can be found in the stricter political regime, discipline and more challenging economic and social circumstances in which representatives of those born before 1965 were forced to live. Although already relatively behind in Bulgarian history, historical events of the last century have probably *marked* the respondents' character, which is reflected in high levels of self-regulation.

When analysing the data from the survey of Bulgarian digital entrepreneurs, one more significant generalisation can be made. Although the EI is a product of the five considered competencies – *self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation* of self and others, *empathy* and *social skills*, the predominance of only one of these competencies does not guarantee high EI. That is most clearly highlighted in the results achieved by the representatives of the Baby Boomers. Satisfactory levels of EI, therefore, require efforts in all five directions, as well as a host of other research, such as what accounts for Baby Boomers' Optimism and where their low levels of Empathy come from, why Millennials and Generation Z have poorer Social skills, even though both demographics grew up in a situation of unprecedented connectivity, characterised by open borders, diverse communications, and unlimited opportunities; why exactly Generation X demonstrates this resilience in all EI elements.

As the literature background clarifies, not all EI components are easily adjustable. Positive or negative tuning, according to Daniel Goleman, may lie in the innate temperament of the individual. The author argues that some people are naturally inclined to act in one way or the other. Still, it is possible, thanks to life experience and inner self-adjustment or seeing that a person is the master of the events he encounters, for the temperament to smoothly and successfully move along the scale from pessimism to optimism (Goleman, 2011).

Not without reason, it can be argued that an individual's self-motivation or optimism, both in his personal life and at work, is directly dependent on the drive or inspiration he feels to complete a task or achieve a goal within his career or personal relationships (Huang, 2022). Inner strength makes an individual put in the necessary effort to achieve success. There are different types of motivation, such as intrinsic motivation (internal locus of control), which comes from the person himself and is driven by self-interest and pleasure, and extrinsic motivation (external locus of control), which comes from external factors such as rewards or incentives (Channell, 2021). For a person to maintain or develop his self-motivation, several factors have an impact: temperament, circumstances over which the individual has no influence, work environment, personal relationships, and others. Overcoming these adverse

factors and challenges nurtures a person's efficacy, allowing them to develop and use their knowledge, skills and competencies (Goleman, 2011).

As stated in the research methodology, the *motivation* indicator in the present study deviates from Goleman's model. The study's author introduced the component to examine the ability of the respondents to motivate others. In the context of entrepreneurship, including digital, a leader's ability to motivate teams and employees is critical. The research shows that this is the least developed competence of respondents belonging to the Baby Boomer generation, which can be seen as a natural result of the other competencies with low values – empathy and social skills. The inability to communicate, on the one hand, and the inability to read others' emotional states logically leads to failure in an area critical to business relationships and activities, such as motivation. Smith *et al.* (2023) argued that people who grew up in harsher and more unpredictable environments, such as abuse or neglect, are less aware and understanding not only of others' emotions but also of their own. The conclusion again gives reason to look for a connection between the emotional evolution of the individual and his past in the context of the already mentioned economy, politics, history, and family.

5.1 Limitations and future research

A significant limitation of the study is the chosen introductory methodology. The chosen method does not allow tracking the results over time for the same respondents, but only for generational groups and economic activities. That dramatically minimises the possibility that inferred data will be reconfirmed or rejected by subsequent research.

A limitation of the methodology contributes to the main weakness of the study: the impossibility of following the change of the EI of a given individual over time, *i.e.* over the years, and focuses on the four main generations – Baby Boomers, X, Y and Z. This makes the conclusions too general for entire generations. Still, the findings are also a suitable base for expanding scientific research in this direction.

A significant limitation of the study is that although the sample has a wide age range and covers the main generational groups, it may only be representative of some of the population. The representatives of the Baby Boomer generation who participate in the research are too few in number of respondents. That signals that the data for this generational group should not be generalised based only on the current analysis, and additional studies are needed.

The reasons for the low activity of those born before 1965 are not the subject of the present research, but it is recommended that they be clarified and considered at the following study stage. Such reasons can be, for example, the weaker digital activity of the Baby Boomer generation, the reported lower levels of empathy and social skills (respectively unresponsiveness to participate in such surveys) or the low employment in digital entrepreneurship. Furthermore, only a Bulgarian model was tested, so it is unclear whether specific Bulgarian or Eastern European cultural features may influence the results. The latter calls for greater caution from researchers in adapting and generalising the current results to other cultures.

The gender factor, which may reject, confirm or modify the obtained results, is also excluded from the analysis. The demographic indicator gender is the subject of a similar study based on the same methodology and conducted by the author of the present study. The data is yet to be presented to the scientific community.

5.2 Theoretical and practical implications

This study adds to the ongoing discourse on the development of EI with age and confirms Sharma's (2017) assertions that general EI may increase with age. Still, the pattern of competence is different, and specific competencies must be developed through training and are not absolutely dependent on the age factor. The study supports the findings (Phillips *et al.*,

2002; Anwar, 2010; Goleman, 2011; Galdona *et al.*, 2018; Gottfredson and Becker, 2023) that EI has the potential to increase with age, but age is not the only determinant for a change. The process is directly dependent on the individual's efforts towards self-knowledge and building relationships.

In addition, the results of the current study can be taken as a supplement to Gottfredson and Becker's (2023) theory that past psychological traumas may cause neural adaptations that impede individuals' EI abilities. Some of the respondents in the present study were born and grew up in an environment of severe socio-economic and political conditions, which, as a possible cause of conscious or unconscious psychological traumas, may reflect in underestimated EI competencies. Therefore, although it is permissible to use general models in the measurement process, in the process of increasing EI, personal traits, cultural differences, historical burdens and other factors should be taken into account. That would illuminate the causal relationship *experience – emotional intelligence*.

The study also raises new research questions. The author's future research aims to develop a methodology measuring and tracking the evolution of individuals' EI over time. Further studies and comparative analyses are needed to prove or not why EI evolved concerning Generations X, Y, and Z but not with Baby Boomers.

The practical applicability of the data lies in the identified relevance of knowledge and experience in the context of organisations, entrepreneurship and teamwork. Similar studies would allow those occupying leadership and managerial positions to know better and motivate their employees and managers from the field of human resources to understand, to a greater extent, the specifics of individual generational groups of employees.

In the meantime, increasing knowledge on the *age-emotional intelligence* axis will allow strategies to be introduced to promote an increase in EI in students, minimise the risk of behavioural addictions, and increase the individual's subjective sense of well-being. Although implementation programs to improve student EI have grown globally, studies still need to be conducted, particularly in Bulgaria. As Maj (2023) points out, a new awareness is needed in the organisational context of academic communities to foster a healthy and creative learning environment. Enhancing the resources promoting the strengths and talents of the people is a way to achieve prosperity and innovative growth in any nation.

6. Conclusions

In the context of more socially oriented societies, investing in highly emotionally intelligent people who seek balance, strive for shared prosperity and make decisions based on self-control and empathy is more urgent than ever.

Regarding evolution, emotional intelligence undoubtedly can improve and build upon itself throughout a human's lifetime. Experience, self-awareness, and learning from interactions with other people can improve emotional intelligence. Specific training programs and exercises to develop emotional intelligence can also help.

The research demonstrates the upward development of emotional intelligence and affirms the independent results of other studies conducted in various periods by different scientists and with diverse methodologies applied.

The study also shows that although emotional intelligence consists of five components: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation of self and others, empathy and social skills, the dominance of one of the elements does not guarantee a high overall individual's emotional intelligence. Therefore, it is necessary to develop all five components in parallel.

In conclusion, the level of emotional intelligence varies from person to person and from generation to generation and depends on many factors, including genetics, environment, education, and experience. The present study confirms that it is incorrect to study this type of intelligence outside the context of the mentioned factors. The signs that distinguish

generational segmentation should also be considered when analysing the emotional intelligence of individual generations since each of them carries the painful (or not) *marks* of its time cycle.

References

- Anwar, Y. (2010), "Emotional intelligence peaks as we enter our 60s, research suggests", *Berkeley News*, available at: <https://news.berkeley.edu/2010/12/16/agingemotion> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Atkins, P. and Con, S. (2005), "Does emotional intelligence change with age?", *Conference: Society for Research in Adult Development*, available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234377636_Does_Emotional_Intelligence_change_with_age (accessed 14th February 2023).
- Bariso, J. (2020), "Should I abbreviate emotional intelligence as EI or EQ? There's only 1 right answer", media, available at: <https://www.inc.com/justin-bariso/should-i-abbreviate-emotional-intelligence-as-ei-or-eq-theres-only-1-right-answer.html> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Barr, P. (2023), "Relationships of nursing stress and trait emotional intelligence with mental health in neonatal intensive care unit nurses: a cross-sectional correlational study", *Australian Critical Care*, Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 258-264, doi: [10.1016/j.aucc.2023.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aucc.2023.07.005).
- Borrajó, E., Calvete, E. and Urquijo, I. (2023), "Negative self-talk in runners: emotional intelligence and perceived stress as explanatory factors", *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, Vol. 70 No. January 2024, 102545, doi: [10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102545](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102545).
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T. (2013), "Can you really improve your emotional intelligence?", *Harvard Business Review*, available at: <https://hbr.org/2013/05/can-you-really-improve-your-em> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Channell, M. (2021), "Daniel Goleman's emotional intelligence in leadership: how to improve motivation in your team", TSW Training, available at: <https://www.tsw.co.uk/blog/leadership-and-management/daniel-goleman-emotional-intelligence/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Chen, Y., Peng, Y. and Fang, P. (2016), "Emotional intelligence mediates the relationship between age and subjective well-being", *International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, Vol. 83 No. 2, pp. 91-107, doi: [10.1177/0091415016648705](https://doi.org/10.1177/0091415016648705).
- Cherry, K. (2023), "5 Key emotional intelligence skills", Verywell Mind, available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/components-of-emotional-intelligence-2795438> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Cherry, K. (2024), "Emotional Intelligence: how we perceive, evaluate, express, and control emotions", *Verywell Mind*, available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-emotional-intelligence-2795423> (accessed 20th February 2024).
- Craig, H. (2019), "The theories of Emotional Intelligence explained", *Positive Psychology*, available at: <https://positivepsychology.com/emotional-intelligence-theories/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- DEV (2021), "Колко tech хора всъщност работят в България?", [How many tech people actually work in Bulgaria?], [In Bulgarian], available at: <https://bit.ly/46GyNI5> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Di Fabio, A. and Kenny, M.E. (2016), "Promoting well-being: the contribution of emotional intelligence", *Frontiers in Psychology*, Vol. 7, 211375, doi: [10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01182](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01182).
- Dimock, M. (2019), "Defining generations: where Millennials end and Generation Z begins", *Pew Research Center*, available at: <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/01/17/where-millennials-end-and-generation-z-begins/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Economy (2019), "Кои са поколенията Z, Y, X и бейби бумърите?", [Who are Generations Z, Y, X and Baby Boomers?], [In Bulgarian], available at: <https://www.economy.bg/article/view/37047> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Fernández-Martínez, E., López-Alonso, A.I., Marqués-Sánchez, P., Martínez-Fernández, M.C., Sánchez-Valdeón, L. and Liébana-Presa, C. (2019), "Emotional Intelligence, sense of coherence,

- engagement and coping: a cross-sectional study of University students' health", *Sustainability*, Vol. 11 No. 24, p. 6953, doi: [10.3390/su11246953](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11246953).
- Fernández-Martínez, E., Sutil-Rodríguez, E. and Liébana-Presa, C. (2023), "Internet addiction and Emotional Intelligence in University nursing students: a cross-sectional study", *Heliyon*, Vol. 9 No. 9, e19482, doi: [10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19482](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19482).
- Freedman, J. (2021), "Emotional intelligence gaps across the generations", *Six Seconds*, available at: <https://www.6seconds.org/2021/10/26/emotional-intelligence-generations/> (accessed 20th February 2024).
- Fuchs, R.M. (2022), "Links, fit or sacrifice: job embeddedness and intention to quit among Generation Y", *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, Vol. 31 No. 2, pp. 160-175, doi: [10.1108/EJMBE-05-2021-0156](https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-05-2021-0156).
- Galdona, N., Martínez Taboada, C., Etxeberria, I., Urdaneta, E. and Aldaz, E. (2018), "Positive aging: the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological, social and physical well-being", *MOJ Gerontol Ger*, Vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 9-11, doi: [10.15406/mojgg.2018.03.00073](https://doi.org/10.15406/mojgg.2018.03.00073).
- Goleman, D. (2011), "Емоционална интелигентност", [Emotional intelligence], Iztok-Zapad, Sofiya, Bulgaria, ISBN: 978-954-321-888-2 [In Bulgarian]
- Gottfredson, R.K. and Becker, W.J. (2023), "How past trauma impacts emotional intelligence: examining the connection", *Frontiers in Psychology*, Vol. 14, 1067509, doi: [10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1067509](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1067509).
- Huang, R.-T. (2022), "Exploring the roles of self-determined motivation and perceived organisational support in organisational change", *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print, doi: [10.1108/EJMBE-03-2022-0056](https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-03-2022-0056).
- Humintell (2011), "Emotional Intelligence gets better with age", available at: <https://www.humintell.com/2011/01/emotional-intelligence-gets-better-with-age/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Jakubik, M. and Mürsepp, P. (2022), "From knowledge to wisdom: will wisdom management replace knowledge management?", *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, Vol. 31 No. 3, pp. 367-389, doi: [10.1108/EJMBE-07-2021-0219](https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-07-2021-0219).
- Johnson, N., Lahti, D. and Blumstein, D. (2012), "Combating the assumption of evolutionary progress: lessons from the decay and loss of traits", *Evolution: Education and Outreach*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 128-138, doi: [10.1007/s12052-011-0381-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12052-011-0381-y).
- Kennedy, J. (2020), "You can't improve EQ but you can improve Feeling Intelligence", *Psychology Today*, available at: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/brain-reboot/202011/you-cant-improve-eq-you-can-improve-feeling-intelligence> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Kennedy, J. (no date), "Why you can't improve your EQ but can improve your Emotional Intelligence", *Mind Journal*, available at: <https://themindsjournal.com/why-cannot-improve-emotional-intelligence/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Kostadinova, I. (2019), "Емоционалната и социалната интелигентност – влияещ фактор върху резултатите от лекарския труд", [Emotional and social intelligence – influencing factor for the results of medical work], Akademichno izdatelstvo "Rusenski universitet", Ruse, Bulgaria, ISBN 978-954-712-760-9 [In Bulgarian]
- Kuday, A. and Erdoğan, Ö. (2023), "Relationship between emotional intelligence and disaster response self-efficacy: a comparative study in nurses", *International Emergency Nursing*, Vol. 70, 101319, doi: [10.1016/j.ienj.2023.101319](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ienj.2023.101319).
- Maj, J. (2023), "Organisational culture and leadership as facilitators of creativity and innovation: insights from the ICT sector in Poland in a post-COVID-19 reality", *Journal of Economics and Management*, Vol. 45 No. 1, pp. 182-215, doi: [10.22367/jem.2023.45.09](https://doi.org/10.22367/jem.2023.45.09).
- Medium (2018), "How digitally aware are the different generations", available at: <https://medium.com/@thedigitaldunk/how-digitally-aware-are-the-different-generations-aab7fe058200> (accessed 20th November 2023).

- MindTools (n.d.), “Emotional intelligence in leadership”, available at: https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newLDR_45.htm (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Move, B.G. (2017), “Мисия дигитален бизнес в България”, [Mission digital business in Bulgaria], [In Bulgarian], available at: <https://move.bg/misiya-digitalen-biznes-v-blgariya> (accessed 14th February 2023)
- NSI (2021), “Използване на информационни и комуникационни технологии в предприятията през 2020 година”, [Use of information and communication technologies in enterprises in 2020], National Statistical Institute (Bulgaria) [In Bulgarian], available at: <https://bit.ly/46HfCxC> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- NSI (2022), “Брой предприятия по сектори и по групи според броя на заетите в тях лица за 2021 година”, [Number of enterprises by sectors and by groups according to the number of persons employed in them for 2021], National Statistical Institute (Bulgaria), [In Bulgarian], available at: <https://bit.ly/47FHqnr> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Phillips, L., MacLean, R. and Allen, R. (2002), “Age and the understanding of emotions: neuropsychological and sociocognitive perspectives”, *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, Vol. 57 No. 6, pp. 526-530, doi: [10.1093/geronb/57.6.P526](https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/57.6.P526)
- Reilly, A. and Karounos, T. (2009), “Exploring the link between Emotional Intelligence and cross-cultural leadership effectiveness”, *Journal of International Business and Cultural Studies*, available at: <https://bit.ly/49TNqKP> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Sharma, D. (2017), “Impact of age on emotional intelligence and its components”, *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, Vol. I No. I, pp. 13-20, available at: <https://www.rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/Digital-Library/Vol.1&Issue1/13-20.pdf> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Smith, A. (2018), “Does emotional intelligence (EQ) improve with age?”, LifeConnect24, available at: <https://www.lifeconnect24.co.uk/blog/emotional-intelligence/> (accessed 20th November 2023).
- Smith, R., Steklis, H.D., Steklis, N., Weihs, K.L., Allen, J.J.B. and Lane, R.D. (2023), “Lower emotional awareness is associated with greater early adversity and faster life history strategy”, *Evolutionary Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 1-15, doi: [10.1037/ebbs0000282](https://doi.org/10.1037/ebbs0000282).
- Wezowski, K. and Penton-Voak, I. (2023), “Associations between workplace emotional intelligence and micro expression recognition”, *Acta Psychologica*, Vol. 240, 104046, doi: [10.1016/j.actpsy.2023.104046](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2023.104046).
- Wood, R. and Tolley, H. (2003), “Test your emotional intelligence: how to assess and boost your EQ”, Kogan Page, ISBN 978-0749437329.
- Xue, S., Kong, F., Song, Y. and Liu, J. (2023), “Neural correlates of social interaction anxiety and their relation to emotional intelligence: a resting-state fMRI study”, *Neuroscience Letters*, Vol. 818, 137475, doi: [10.1016/j.neulet.2023.137475](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2023.137475).
- Zadorozhny, B.S., Petrides, K., Jongerling, J., Cuppello, S. and Van der Linden, D. (2024), “Assessing the temporal stability of a measure of trait emotional intelligence: systematic review and empirical analysis”, *Personality and Individual Differences*, Vol. 217, 112467, doi: [10.1016/j.paid.2023.112467](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2023.112467).

Corresponding author

Ana Todorova can be contacted at: attodorova@uni-ruse.bg

For instructions on how to order reprints of this article, please visit our website:

www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/licensing/reprints.htm

Or contact us for further details: permissions@emeraldinsight.com